

Analysis and optimization on the transport infrastructure management in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Drawing upon Inter-organizational relations theory and cognitive theories, this study builds a research framework in which to examine how financial support and government support shape the transport infrastructure of Bangladesh. Using survey data from Bangladeshi firms with two key informants, we find that financial support and government support both serve as critical drivers for the transportation infrastructure. This research is divided into six stages, research background, literature review, conceptual framework, research methodology, results, and conclusion. This study comprises the preliminary research exploring the mechanism by which government support, and financial support influence the transportation infrastructure of Bangladesh. International collaboration is used as a moderator in this research to check whether it positively enhances the relationship between financial support and government support with transportation infrastructure or not

Keywords: Drivers, transport infrastructure, GDP

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Introduction

This study aims to investigate the impact of government support, financial support in shaping the transport infrastructure of Bangladesh. Transport is the critical factor that led to the GDP growth of the country, therefore it is critical to analyze the factors that could have a strong impact on the transport infrastructure. Here in this research author is using two variables (government support and financial support) to check their impact on transport infrastructure. To improve the infrastructure transportation system government support is the critical factor; government can provide subsidies to the transportation and should provide tax relief to the construction companies to motivate them to invest more in the improvement of the infrastructure. Similarly, financial institutions are critical for providing financial support to construction projects. when organizations get financial support from the financial institutions at possibly lower tax rates then it increases the risk-taking behaviors of the companies and they always invest more to improve the infrastructure of the transportation system. On the other hand, when the financial institutions are not supportive and companies are not able to have enough finances then it will influence research and development processes as that requires financial support. So financial support and government support are the critical factors that impact the infrastructure of a transportation system. The secondary objective of this research is to analyze the moderating role of

international collaboration on the relationship between financial support, government support, and transportation infrastructure.

Bangladesh is a densely populated and low-lying nation. As of the 2021 report Bangladesh's population is around 167.89 million and this population is increasing by 10% annually. The total area of the country is 147,570 sq. km. this shows the population is dense and the major problem faced by the locals is related to transportation activities. It is obvious that in a dense population it will be difficult for the transportation industries to be challenged free.

In Bangladesh, and for every country the role of transportation is very critical as this sector is growing exponentially for the last 20 years at the same time, transportation needs to keep changing its strategy to continuously grow and continuously improve its infrastructure. Around 62% of transportation services increase in the country, and with this increase, several challenges regarding the management of transportation systems are faced by the transportation sector. This research will be focusing on the common challenges faced by the transportation sector by exploring the existing literature and secondly, this research will be exploring the impact of government support on Bangladesh's transport infrastructure management.

Research Background

Transportation infrastructure is the critical factor that led to the successful economic development of the country, it not only supports the GDP of the country but also enhances the well-being of individuals (OECD, 2013). For instance, every business success or failure is based on the supply chain and for supply chains organizations need to have a quality transportation system. Therefore, transportation is the critical factor that influences the business's performance, therefore it is critical to improve the transportation infrastructure of the company (OECD, 2013). Transportation infrastructure is based on financial investments, when the government is providing support to the transportation sectors it led to the influence of the transportation sector of the country (OECD, 2013). Transportation is defined as the use of different means to transfer people, materials from one place to the other. Transportation is an important factor that contributes to the economy of every country (Wang et al., 2018) and it contributed to the development of socioeconomic and improve the quality of life by connecting different cities (Liu et al., 2015). From an industrial point of view, transportation is the key for businesses' supply chain, different transportation means are being used by the organizations to get the raw material from their suppliers. Then to send the finish good to their customers or distributors. The supply chain sustainability of a firm depends on the transportation system of that organization (Doyle, 2009). Therefore, the transportation system of a country or a business contributes to the success. economic development of a country highly depends on the transportation system as well (Jiang et al., 2016 & Chen and Haynes, 2017).

Transportation infrastructure impacts the performance of other sectors; therefore, it is required to improve the infrastructure of the transportation system of a country. When the transportation system is of good qualities it results in the improvement of supply chains of other businesses and results in the smooth flow of goods from one place to the other. Most of the organizations are having their suppliers in different cities and even countries and transportation is the key for on time delivery of products. So, this point makes this research study more meaningful.

At the same time, as transportation routes are connecting different industries and these routes are very complex (Rodrigue, 2016). The poor management regarding the transport infrastructure led to mishaps (accidents) that negatively affected economic development and human life. Therefore, the first challenge faced by the transportation sector is regarding the management of the routes to avoid any uncertainty associated with the transport (Cantos, Gumbau-Albert, & Maudos, 2005). Most of the time it is not possible for the organizations to have all the finance, therefore, collaboration is the critical factor for the infrastructure of transportation. So, when organizations collaborate they can share the finances and support the infrastructure by providing enough finances that result in the improvement of the infrastructure. Through collaboration, the overall financial support can be increased and so the infrastructure of the country. International collaboration will enable organizations to improve their transport infrastructure across the

borders and within the country so that they can have better infrastructure across the country. For instance, Bangladesh can collaborate with China to improve the transportation infrastructure like Pakistan did for the CPEC project. Through these international collaborations, Bangladeshi transportation can get financial assistance from China and can improve their transportation infrastructure.

Transportation infrastructure is not easy to be defined but can be identified. The key factor and the characteristics that identify the infrastructure are the large investment, complicated risks, and longer construction periods. Countries that are having huge investments will make them able to construct new routes and improve their infrastructure. Countries like China and America where the transportation routes are very well designed and different routes for different kinds of vehicles show the better planning and better infrastructure of the country. This better planning is the result of having high investments, skilled workers, and most importantly support from the government. On the other hand, countries like Bangladesh that is not strong financially as compared to the developed countries like China and America still facing challenges related to investment, government support, and skilled workers. So, there is a strong need to analyze the Bangladesh transportation infrastructure and then to give quality suggestions to the transportation policymakers to overcome these challenges.

This research will be exploring existing theoretical kinds of literature regarding the challenges associated with the infrastructure of transportation and find out the solution by comparing the transportation infrastructure of Bangladesh to the countries with quality transportation infrastructure. Secondly, the author will be elaborating on the impact of government support and financial support impact transportation infrastructure.

In this research, the author will be collecting data from the officials who are working in the transportation sector of Bangladesh and try to acquire knowledge regarding the problems faced by them after getting their opinion on how government and financial support impact the infrastructure conclusion will be drawn. According to the best of author knowledge, previous researches lag to provide a shred of empirical evidence regarding the impact of financial and government support on the infrastructure of the transportation system. Moreover, few similar types of research have been conducted in developed countries but this research will be providing the perception of a developing economy that will enrich the existing literature.

Research Significance

The transportation system of a country impact all of the businesses operating in that country, for instance, most of the businesses are having suppliers in different regions, cities, and even in different countries. The major problem faced by the organizations is related to the on-time delivery of products or the raw material to the manufacturers because of poor transportation infrastructure and lower capacity of roads as compared to the actual demands, therefore to improve the performance of other businesses, transportation plays a critical role. This impact of transportation on other businesses makes this research more significant.

Further, with the advent of e-commerce, customers want products on their doorsteps and on time, from the local as well as from the international companies. For instance, Alibaba is the platform which is delivering products in Asian countries and for the on-time delivery of the products, there must be quality infrastructure. So, with e-commerce, the requirement for quality transportation infrastructure has been increased, and this research is focusing on improving the infrastructure of the transportation system which makes this research study more meaningful.

Bangladesh is an emerging economy and the economic development of the country is depending on its transportation systems. Currently, the major problem faced by Bangladesh is that they are having a smaller area and a huge population. The dense population of the country required a large number of vehicles and for that Bangladesh needs to improve the infrastructure. This research will be exploring this factor as well and it make this research more significant.

To improve the infrastructure, Bangladesh needs to have strong financial support and development support from the private and government sectors. To overcome the investment challenges, Bangladesh BRT needs to collaborate with

other countries for financial support. For example, the CPEC model can be copied, CPEC is the collaboration between Pakistan and China. This corridor will help Pakistan (a developing economy) to improve its transportation infrastructure and results in the economic development of the country. This result will be exploring the impact of international collaboration and it's how it strengthens the impact of investments on transportation investments. This is the first sign of this research. Further how government support towards the private road construction will help this sector will be elaborated and it will make this research more significant.

Secondly, the economic development of a country depends on the businesses operating in the country. The businesses include different transportation activities for the transfer of goods and services, and the success of an organization the sustainable and quality transportation system is the key factor.

For instance, during the Covid-19 situation, most of the businesses fail just because of having unsustainable transportation systems. Organizations were not able to receive the raw material from the suppliers and were not able to deliver the product to the customers. In Bangladesh, most of the multinational auto industries did not sell and manufacture a single product because of the unavailability of raw material and lockdown situation all across the country i.e. Suzuki motors. Because of their main suppliers in Japan. Covid strongly affected the business development in Bangladesh. To elaborate the existing literature and to find out the possible solution for the Bangladesh transportation infrastructure to deal with the environmental uncertainty is the second important significance of this research. So, these are the significances associated with our research.

Research Purpose

This research mainly has two purposes. The first one is to theoretically analyze the challenges faced by Bangladesh transport infrastructure management and then to collect primary data to empirically analyze the impact of different variables on the Bangladesh transportation system.

The purpose of this research is to

1. Explore the challenges associated with the Bangladesh Transportation system
2. Explore the financial challenges faced by the Bangladesh transportation infrastructure
3. Explore the impact of government support in shaping the transportation infrastructure
4. Explore the impact of development support in shaping the transportation infrastructure
5. How collaboration with other countries can help Bangladesh to improve its transportation infrastructure?
6. Explore the impact of transportation infrastructure on business performance in Bangladesh.

Research Questions

Based on the purpose and the objective of this research, the following research questions were designed by the author.

1. What are the challenges faced by the transport infrastructure management of Bangladesh transportation?
2. What are the financial challenges faced by the infrastructure management of Bangladesh transportation?
3. What is the impact of government support in shaping the transportation infrastructure?
4. What is the impact of development support in shaping the transportation infrastructure?
5. How collaboration can strengthen the impact of development support and government support on infrastructure management in Bangladesh?
6. Why transportation system of Bangladesh is important for the development of the businesses operating in Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

This research is empirical, and primary data will be collected through questionnaires. After data collection, author will be employing SPSS software to run statistical analysis to test the designed hypothesis. Regression analysis will be adopted for hypothesis testing.

Conceptual Framework

This research is based on two independent variables (financial support, government support), moderating variable (international collaboration) and one dependent variable, which is development of transportation infrastructure. Financial support is the financial assistance that enable organizations to complete the projects. Financial support is the availability of sufficient resources that an organization has to achieve its objectives and goals. Financial support is also defined as the assets that are provided by the external and internal stakeholders to the company for the completion of projects. Financial support is also defined as a critical factor that led to successful project completion. The second independent variable of this research is government support, and it is defined as the government policies, that are in the favor of the businesses. Government support is having significance and a decisive role in shaping the transport system of a country (Adolf et al., 2018). Government investments in the transportation sectors enable the countries to improve their infrastructure (Albalate and Bel, 2012). Nevertheless, the government's role as a central part of economic growth policies is an active force in the business world, because it promotes how the supply chains of the businesses operate in a determined region and plays a major role in investments that led to improved infrastructures (Mari Farinós et al. 2017). The moderating variable is the international collaboration. Collaboration is defined as the collective efforts that are made to achieve the objectives of a firm. international collaboration is the partnership between businesses or individuals who are living in two different countries. Collaboration is the combined efforts of different firms and shareholders to ensure the success of a company by bringing new products to the market (Luzzini, et al. 2015). International collaboration is defined as the alliances among different parties, businesses or individual that belongs to different countries.

Collaboration enables organizations to reduce the uncertainty in the environment (Kienzle et al., 1997). Collaborative innovation allows organizations to get more access to creative ideas, reduction in redundant operations, increase in power and enables organizations to solve the issues which are beyond the domain of a single firm (Stanely, 2004). IOR theory helps in recognizing the needs for cooperation, sharing resources, power and policies in achieving the common goals. IOR further briefs about the positive impact of collaboration on an organization's performance (Huin et al., 2016). Entrepreneurs always prefer to collaborate with successful organizations to get the advantage from their resources. IOR explains how small and medium enterprises (SME's) can get benefit through collaboration. This theory also describes the role of collaboration in enhancing the performance of organizations. Inter-organization relationship theory also focuses on the antecedents required for long term partnerships and explains the involvement of suppliers, competitors and end users in cooperation process to make collaboration effective. IOR emphasizes on the relationship patterns from higher level to the lower level i.e. relationship pattern between organizations and among the member of various organizations (Dyer and Singh, 2014). For example, social relationship among different members of an organization is analyzed by this theory. Three distinct academic traditions have influenced studies of inter-organizational interactions and networks. IOR has three different research traditions (Business research, strategic management and organization science). Mainly, inter-organization theory is applied in the field of strategic management. For the last 40 years, researchers have been focusing on the role collaboration among various industries in shaping the firm's performance. International collaboration is used as a moderator in this study and this inter-organizational relations theory is in support of this variable. Institutional theory is focusing on the adaptation and diffusion of new knowledge. Institutional theory explains the hurdles faced by organizations or intuitions in extracting knowledge from the external environment. This theory explains an organization's structure, its norms and values and how new technologies are adopted and assimilated by it. This theory is selected as it supports the independent variables of this research study.

When transportation sector is getting support in term of policies relaxation and financial aid from international as well as local financial institutions it speedup the development process. Therefore this research will be analyzing the positive impact of these variables on development of transportation infrastructure. In the similar manner, when organizations collaborate on international level, it increases the resources of transportation sector will strengthen the development of transportation sector therefore we have used international collaboration as moderating variables of this research study.

After reviewing the literature, there are very few studies that focus on these government and financial support and their effect on the transportation infrastructure. This study is related to government and financial support and how these two factors impact infrastructure of transportation. Further, the secondary objective of this research is to analyze the moderating role of international collaboration strengthening the relationship between government and financial support, and transportation infrastructure. In developing and emerging economies like Bangladesh, practitioners are not focusing on developing transportation infrastructure and this is one of the reasons authors have selected this research to check the impact of government and financial support in shaping the transport infrastructure. Secondly, the literature and market research states that this phenomenon has not been explored in Bangladesh in this manner, thus this study will provide Bangladeshi perspective in a specific area.

Hypothesis Development

H1: Financial Support is positively related to development of transportation infrastructure

H2: Government Support is positively related to development of transportation infrastructure

H3: International Collaboration positively moderates the relationship between financial support and development of transportation infrastructure

H4: International Collaboration positively moderates the relationship between government support and development of transportation infrastructure

For hypothesis testing author will be collecting data by using questionnaires from official working in transportation sector of Bangladesh. In questionnaires author will be asking questions related to government support, financial support, international collaboration, and development of transportation infrastructure and then statistical tool will be implemented to test the hypothesis.

Research Methodology

This chapter discusses the data collection survey, and statistical approaches to function the hypotheses produced. It is achieved by including data collection techniques, tool selection, and samples used to gather data. In end, we conduct reliability and validity checks to determine the model's ability to test.

Research Design

The process of collecting data via research questions in order to investigate and test the necessary information in order to gather proof for whether or not the suggested hypothesis is right can be defined as research designs (Juni, 2014). It is a remarkable framework that defines the relationships between variables that enable effective results to be produced and guides the collection of references and required information (Wiersma et al., 2005). A successful research design

helps and assists the researcher in achieving effective and outstanding results in his research work, as well as increasing the study's value and utility.

Generally, there are two kinds of research design methods used in social sciences: quantitative and qualitative (Alrawabdeh, 2014). Because of its usefulness and reliability, the quantitative approach is preferred by the majority of researchers (Bernard, 2000). The reason for choosing a quantitative approach plan over another is that it can produce validated as well as accurate results (Chase, 2016). In this case, using a questionnaire survey is useful and significant (Bowling, 2005). The research design also explains the various components of the study, such as the research hypothesis variables, and a few analyses (regression and correlation) that are used in the study.

This study is classified as a "descriptive study." A descriptive study is one in which data is collected by the use of questionnaires and the findings are compared (Koch, 2014). Descriptive analysis helps researchers in accurately describing the features of the sample population in order to gain insights into the frequency with which information is encountered, as well as the relationship among the study's variables (Dulock, 1993). Convenience sampling and convenience-based data collection strategies have been used to gather data from the transport sector of Bangladesh.

A research design is well planned to respond to all research questions (Cooper et al., 2005). It is an outstanding system that defines the associations between variables that allow producing effective results and directs the selection of references and necessary knowledge (Wiersma et al., 2005). The test method involves two approaches; quantitative and qualitative. In this analysis, a quantitative sectional sample design is introduced. Cross-sectional sampling is important to study the features of observed events and investigate potential relationships between them (Leed et al., 2001). Therefore, utilizing a survey research design with various statistical tools in this analysis was effective in identifying the association between entrepreneurial expectations and independent variables (Creswell, 2009).

Research design has a strong impact on the size of the sample. The data collection method is a very important part of any empirical research because designed hypothesis results, which is the primary objective of the research highly depend on the reliability and validity of data. Data collection through the survey is a widely used technique (Pfleeger and Kitchenham, 2001). There are different factors like available time, cost and response rate, etc. which are considered before conducting a survey (Cobanoglu et al., 2001). There are two types of techniques used for data collection; interviews and surveys (William M.K. 2006). In this research, the main objective is to get as many responses as possible but due to time constraints survey method was used as a source of data collection. Data was collected from different firm managers working in different companies. Once the data collection is finished next step is to analyze the data reliability, validity, and different test are carried out to check the results which are explained in chapter five. Another important decision that has to be made while testing data is to identify the pool of respondents. For the present research, senior managers from different parents, subsidiaries, and newly established companies were selected to get the data. To test the current study's hypotheses, it was necessary to involve the higher management since the questionnaires were designed according to their understanding of the firm.

There are three types of research designs: experimental, quasi-experimental, and non-experimental. The experimental research design is concerned with the cause-and-effect relationship of the variables in the study. In an experimental testing process, the researcher modifies the independent variable and evaluates whether the dependent variable changed in response to the independent variable. Typically, laboratory testing designs are carried out in laboratories. There is just one difference in between quasi-experimental research design and experimental research design: the environments or topics in the quasi-experimental research design are not selected at random. The quasi-experimental research design conducts research in particular settings or does not choose the study's topic at random, while the experimental research design conducts research in random settings. The researcher evaluates the relationship between the study's variables in a non-experimental test design. A non-experimental research design explores the relationship between variables to determine whether an occurrence happened. Unlike in an experimental research

design, the independent variables in a non-experimental research design cannot be modified. This thesis makes use of a non-experimental testing design (Glesne, 2015).

All analysis techniques are found to be commonly used in research. To analyses the findings, the qualitative research approach employs extensive study of a subject with the support of live interviews with professionals in the field using open-ended questioning and evaluation that involves grounded theory. The quantitative research methodology, on the other hand, collects data from a large sample population through survey methods including survey questionnaires and interpretation, which includes quantitative models, to draw conclusions and findings from the data. However, quantitative research findings can be generalized since data from the sample population is gathered in greater quantities, whereas qualitative research findings are special to the analysis and cannot be generalized (Babbie, 2013).

This thesis utilizes a quantitative analysis technique. The quantitative research methodology makes use of numerical data and derives useful information from it using statistical analysis or hypothesis testing of the research model. Using the survey approach and standardized questionnaires with closed-ended questions, a larger sample of data is obtained from the target population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). It was chosen because a larger study, involving more subjects and allowing for more generalization of findings, could be conducted. Furthermore, as data relates to closed-ended knowledge, only a few variables are involved.

For this research study author have adopted primary data collection through questionnaires and then based on those questionnaires author have conducted analysis to analyze the impact of government support, financial support in shaping the transportation infrastructure.

Questionnaire Design

Variables	Items	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Government Support	The following descriptions are about the support your company has received from the government in completion of your company’s transportation tasks; to which extent you agree with the descriptions.							
	Top management enthusiastically supports the adoption of new technologies	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Our organization has allocated adequate resources to adoption of new technologies and innovations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Our organization actively encourages employees to use the new technologies in their tasks	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Our organization is aware of the benefits of new technologies and innovations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Financial Support								
	Financial support can make your firm's manufacturing more effective.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Financial support can make your firm's research and development more effective	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Financial support can make your firm's product service and support more effective	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

	Financial support can help your firm to improve firm operations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Financial support can help your firm effectively manages finances throughout the product development program in line with ongoing contract	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
International Collaboration	Collaboration with international financial institutions enable us to improve the infrastructure of the company	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	International collaboration will assist us in making strategies to ensure the success of transportation infrastructure project	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	International collaboration is critical for the successful implementation of the transport infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Transport Infrastructure	We are making strategies to improve the transport infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Through government support we are improving our transport infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Infrastructure is improved to increase the capacity of the transportation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Continuous road maps are built to ensure the improved transport infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Sampling Strategy

Owing to several valid purposes, it is not possible to obtain data from the entire population. A proper sampling technique is employed in the data collection process. A sample can be described as a subset or a portion of the entire population in simple terms or a section (Webster, 1985; Bryman, 2016). The probability technique or the non-probability technique, which is defined as the sample, can be used to draw this section or subset. As per Cooper (2011), using a sample has many advantages, including being inexpensive and taking little time to gather data.

Both forms of sampling give each member/observation an equal chance and the ability to choose from a sample (Sugiyono, 2017).

The sample size is a subset of the population and it allows the researcher to draw conclusions that are generalizable to the given population (Sekaran, 2006). So, the sample truly represents the population and enables a researcher to generalize its properties and characteristics to the entire population. However, in our case sampling is difficult to do like the total number of populations is not available. Thus, a nonprobability sampling technique based on a conventional approach is suitable for this study.

For empirical researches size of the sample has been defined by many researchers. For example, according to Hair (2010), for every variable, it is mandatory to have at least five values and this is the lower limit but the most appropriate form of assessment is the 10:1 ratio (10 samples per subject). According to another research and experimental study should have at least data set of 50 values and according to Wilcox (2010), there must be at least 100 values for empirical research.

Convenience sampling is pre-owned in this research study. The exact population of service-based firms in Bangladesh is unknown, and according to researchers, when the exact population size is unknown, it is appropriate to choose a non-probability sampling method, that's why convenience sampling was used. Time and resource constraints can also

be solved using this strategy. For this method convenience sampling is adopted to collect data and then to run by using statistical techniques.

Data Analysis Method

Different analytical measures, such as population frequencies, descriptive statistics, and correlation matrix and regression analysis, are adopted to see whether the theories support this analysis or not. Reliabilities of instruments are checked to make sure that outcomes are valid. Also, we applied descriptive analysis to study features of data like the midpoint of data and deviation from the mean.

Co-relation Analysis

We applied correlation analysis to detect association among variables and to detect any possibility of multi collinearity. The doubt of multi collinearity is further verified via variance inflation test (VIF) to avoid discrepancies in regression analysis. The scope of this research is to find the association between the independent variable (government support and financial support) and the dependent variable (transportation infrastructure), and this correlation analysis is used. In correlation analysis, if the value of coefficient (r) is more than ± 0.50 then this means the association between the two variables is strong (Taylor, 1990). If the coefficient value is between ± 0.3 to ± 0.49 then this means they have a moderate relationship and if the coefficient is 0 then this means both variables have no relationship between them.

Regression Analysis

In end, we applied step-wise multiple regression to test study hypotheses. This test will be used to examine the effect of IVs on the DV. This test will tell which factor has a direct impact on the dependent variable and which factor have no impact on the dependent variable. Regression analysis consists of a model summary, ANOVA table, and coefficient. In the ANOVA table, if the value of p will be less than 0.05 then this will indicate a strong association among the IVs and DV.

In the model summary, the R^2 indicates that when there are changes in independent variables then there will be a specific percentage of effect on the dependent variable. In linear regression models, the R-Squared value also shows the level of the association between the linear model and the DVs. The R-squared value varies from 0 to 1. If the R-square value is closer to 0 it means the fit is poor when the R square value is closer to 1 it means the fit is good. In general, the goodness-of-fit of multiple regression is verified by the R-Square value and 10% or 0.1 is acceptable.

The significance test of the regression coefficient can reveal the degree to which each independent variable has a linear relationship with a specific dependent variable. The difference in the DV can be easily described by IVs. If there is a significant link among them, the independent variable will be kept in the regression model; otherwise, it will be removed.

The significance test of linear regression is tested by F-statistics. If the F statistic is significant, it implies that the model representing the linear association among all IVs and a particular DV is appropriate. Otherwise, it is explained that the model cannot describe the association among the variables. In general, the regression analysis has a high degree of fitting, then its significance is relatively high. The results are listed in chapter 5.

Results

This chapter is based on the statistical analysis and their interpretation. This chapter contains demographic analysis, frequency analysis, reliability, validity, correlation, regression analysis to test the hypothesis.

Software

In this research we have used SPSS software and datasheet of the software can be seen in below.

	Firm Size	Firm Age	Experience	GS1	GS2	GS3	GS4	FS1	FS2	FS3	FS4	FS5	InCI
1	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	3.00	5.00	3.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00
2	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00
3	1.00	3.00	3.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00
4	4.00	4.00	3.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
5	3.00	3.00	2.00	7.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	5.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	6.00	6.00
6	5.00	2.00	3.00	7.00	3.00	4.00	7.00	3.00	7.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	7.00
7	1.00	1.00	3.00	7.00	1.00	1.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	3.00	6.00	7.00
8	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
9	7.00	7.00	2.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
10	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	2.00	2.00	5.00	3.00	2.00
11	7.00	7.00	2.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00
12	10.00	5.00	2.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
13	1.00	3.00	3.00	7.00	7.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	7.00	6.00	5.00	5.00
14	6.00	1.00	3.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	5.00	5.00
15	2.00	2.00	4.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	6.00	6.00
16	1.00	1.00	3.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00
17	3.00	3.00	3.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	6.00	6.00	7.00
18	4.00	4.00	3.00	6.00	5.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
19	2.00	2.00	3.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
20	5.00	3.00	3.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	5.00	7.00
21	4.00	4.00	3.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	5.00
22	5.00	5.00	3.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	6.00
23	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	5.00	3.00	4.00	6.00

Frequency Analysis

Firm Age

Data was collected from 153 respondents. Out of 153, 20 respondents were working in transport industries having ages of 0-5 years. There were 25 respondents from transport industries having ages of 6 to 10 years. 15 were working in the firm having age of 11 to 15 and 24 were from transport industries which were established 16 to 20 years ago. Only 29 respondents were from transport industries having age of 21 to 25 years. 24 firms are having age of 26-30 and 16 were having age over 30.

Table 1 Firm Age

Firm Age groups	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative percentage
0-5	20	13.0	13.0	13
6-10	25	16.3	16.3	29.3
11-15	15	9.9	9.9	39.2
16-20	24	15.7	15.7	54.9
21-25	29	19.0	19.0	73.9
26-30	24	15.7	15.7	89.5
31-35	16	10.5	10.5	100
Total	153	100	100	

Experience

Second control variable of this research study is the experience of the respondents and frequency analysis of experience is listed in the table below.

Table 2 Experience

Experience	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative percentage
0-5	40	26.1	26.1	26.1
6-10	19	12.4	12.4	38.5
11-15	17	11.1	11.1	49.6
16-20	19	12.4	12.4	62
21-25			19	12.4
				74.4

26-30	21	13.7	13.7	88.1
31-35	18	11.9	11.9	100
Total	153	100	100	

Descriptive Statistics

Table below showing the descriptive analysis of the variables used in this study. From the table it can be seen very clearly that the mean of all the variable used in the study is between 5 and 6 that means all most of the respondents agree and strongly agree.

Reliability Test

Reliability test is the very first test to check the reliability of the data. Validity of the data depends on the value of the Cronbach’s Alpha. If the value of the Cronbach’s alpha is greater than 0.6 it means the data is reliable and if the value of the Cronbach’s alpha is greater than 0.7 that means the data is very much suitable for the further analysis. From the table below we can clearly see that the lowest value of the Cronbach’s alpha is 0.714, which means all the variables are reliable for the analysis.

Table 3 Reliability

Variable	Cronbach’s alpha
Government Support	0.805
Financial Support	0.714
International Collaboration	0.816
Transport Infrastructure	0.858

Validity Test

Validity of the data can further be explained on the basis of the value of composite reliability. If the reliability values are greater than 0.6 that means the data, set is valid.

Table 4 Validity

Variables	Items	Factor Loading	Composite Reliability
Government Support $\alpha = 0.805$ AVE = 0.681	The following descriptions are about the support your company has received from the government in completion of your company’s transportation tasks; to which extent you agree with the descriptions.		
	1. Top management enthusiastically supports the adoption of new technologies	0.767	
	2. Our organization has allocated adequate resources to adoption of new technologies and innovations	0.824	

	3. Our organization actively encourages employees to use the new technologies in their tasks	0.855	0.895
	4. Our organization is aware of the benefits of new technologies and innovations	0.852	
Financial Support $\alpha = 0.714$ AVE = .676	1. Financial support can make your firm's manufacturing more effective.	0.862	
	2. Financial support can make your firm's research and development more effective	0.790	
	3. Financial support can make your firm's product service and support more effective	0.826	
	4. Financial support can help your firm to improve firm operations	0.808	0.893
	5. Financial support can help your firm effectively manages finances throughout the product development program in line with ongoing contract	0.851	
International Collaboration $\alpha = 0.816$ AVE = 0.653	1. Collaboration with international financial institutions enable us to improve the infrastructure of the company	.807	0.849
	2. International collaboration will assist us in making strategies to ensure the success of transportation infrastructure project	.751	
	3. International collaboration is critical for the successful implementation of the transport infrastructure	.863	
Transport Infrastructure $\alpha = 0.858$ AVE = 0.707	1. We are making strategies to improve the transport infrastructure	.858	
	2. Through government support we are improving our transport infrastructure	.774	
	3. Infrastructure is improved to increase the capacity of the transportation	.853	0.906
	4. Continuous road maps are built to ensure the improved transport infrastructure	.875	

Correlation Analysis

From the correlation table it can be seen that there all the variables are strongly correlated to each other. The effect of the independent variable government support on the dependent variable (Transport infrastructure) is very strong and positive ($r = 0.502^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, there is a strong relationship between the financial support and the dependent variable transportation infrastructure ($r = 0.476^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, the relation between the moderation variable which is international collaboration is having positive and strong impact on the transport infrastructure ($r = 0.512^{**}$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 5 Correlations

	EXP	SIZE	AGE	SP	IA	PE	RD	SCR
EXP	1							
SIZE	.150	1						
AGE	-.075	.254**	1					
Financial Flexibility	.001	-.088	.011	1				
Government Support	.177*	-.025	-.003	.442**	1			
International Collaboration	-.005	-.099	-.004	.583**	.446**	1		
Transport Infrastructure	-.012	-.152	-.001	.502**	.476**	.512**	1	
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Multi collinearities Detection

In 1995 a research was presented in which it is stated that if the variance inflation test values are less than 10, it means there is no multi collinearity and the data is valid. From the VIF table we can clearly see that the values of the VIF are less than 10. The maximum value is 3.460 and the lowest values is 1.379 that means there is no multi collinearity among the variable and data set is reliable and valid.

Table 6 VIF

Predictors	Variance inflation (VIF)
Financial Flexibility	3.460
Government Support	3.294

International Collaboration	1.379
Transport Infrastructure	3.893

Harman's single-factor test

Harman's single-factor test is one of the method to check the covariance among the data set. According to Harman's single-factor test if the percentage of variance is less than 50% that shows there is no multi-collinearity among the data set or the data set is not biased. After analyzing data and employing Harman's single-factor test the percentage of variance is 44.129 which is less than 50% and states the data set is reliable

Table 7 Harman's Single Factor

	Percentage of variance
Harman's Single Factor	0.44129

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is one of the effective methods to test the hypothesis in empirical researches.

H1: Financial Support is positively related to Transport Infrastructure

From the table below it can be seen that the control variables significance value is not valid. For example, the significance value for experience is 0.654 which is not significant, that show the experience factor is controlled and it is not impacting the hypothesis results. Similarly, the firm size significant value is 0.200 that is not significant and showing that firm size is controlled and it is not impacting the overall hypothesis results. Further, the third control variables firm age and results states that firm age factor is controlled as well and not impacting the overall hypothesis results.

Further from the table states that the financial support significant value is 0.000 which means the financial support is having significance impact on the transport infrastructure. Secondly, the unstandardized coefficient value of beta is 0.849 which is positive. That means the impact of the financial support on transport infrastructure is not only significant but positive as well. This results states our first hypothesis is supported by the respondents.

Table 8 Regression Analysis (a)

Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.434	.742		1.934	.055
Experience	-.031	.068	-.026	-.450	.654
Firm Size	-.109	.085	-.077	-1.287	.200
Firm Age	.067	.100	.040	.670	.504
Financial Flexibility	.849	.068	.711	12.471	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Transport Infrastructure

H2: Governmental Support is positively related to Transport Infrastructure

From the table below it can be seen that the control variables significance value is not valid. For example, the significance value for experience is 0.654 which is not significant, that show the experience factor is controlled and it is not impacting the hypothesis results. Similarly, the firm size significant value is 0.200 that is not significant and showing that firm size is controlled and it is not impacting the overall hypothesis results. Further, the third control variables firm age and results states that firm age factor is controlled as well and not impacting the overall hypothesis results.

Further from the table states that the government support significant value is 0.000 which means the government support is having significance impact on the transport infrastructure. Secondly, the unstandardized coefficient value of beta is 0.849, which is positive. That means the impact of the government support on transport infrastructure is not only significant but positive as well. These results states the respondents support our hypothesis.

Table 9 Regression Analysis (a)
Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.434	.742		1.934	.055
Experience	-.031	.068	-.026	-.450	.654
Firm Size	-.109	.085	-.077	-1.287	.200
Firm Age	.067	.100	.040	.670	.504
Government Support	.849	.068	.711	12.471	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Transport Infrastructure

H3: International Collaboration is positively related to Transport Infrastructure

From the table below it can be seen that the control variables significance value is not valid. For example, the significance value for experience is 0.406, which is not significant, that show the experience factor is controlled and it is not impacting the hypothesis results. Similarly, the firm size significant value is 0.112 that is not significant and showing that firm size is controlled and it is not impacting the overall hypothesis results. Further, the third control variables firm age and results states that firm age factor is controlled as well and not impacting the overall hypothesis results.

Further from the table states that the international collaboration significant value is 0.000 which means the international collaboration is having significance impact on the transport infrastructure. Secondly, the unstandardized coefficient value of beta is 0.302, which is positive. That means the impact of the international collaboration on transport infrastructure is not only significant but positive as well. These results states the respondents support our hypothesis.

Table 5-11 Regression Analysis (a)

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.197	.942		5.516	.000
Experience	-.079	.095	-.067	-.834	.406
Firm Size	-.185	.116	-.131	-1.599	.112
Firm Age	.100	.138	.059	.729	.467
International Collaboration	.302	.083	.290	3.659	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Transport Infrastructure

H4: International Collaboration Moderates the Relationship between Financial Support and Transport Infrastructure

From the table below it can be seen that the control variables significance value is not valid. For example, the significance value for experience is 0.707 which is not significant, that show the experience factor is controlled and it is not impacting the hypothesis results. Similarly, the firm size significant value is 0.893 that is not significant and showing that firm size is controlled and it is not impacting the overall hypothesis results. Further, the third control variables firm age and results states that firm age factor is controlled as well land not impacting the overall hypothesis results.

However, from the table below it can be seen that the significant value of interaction between financial support and international collaboration is significant ($P < 0.05$) and the value of beta coefficient is positive (.142) that shows international collaboration positively moderates the relationship between financial support and transport infrastructure.

Table 5-12 Moderation Regression

Moderation Regression					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.485	1.545		2.256	.026
Experience	-.022	.058	-.019	-.377	.707
Firm Size	-.010	.074	-.007	-.135	.893
Firm Age	.084	.087	.049	.970	.334
Financial Support	.424	.326	-.355	-1.301	.195
International Collaboration	.053	.333	-.046	-.161	.873
Interaction (Financial Support * International Collaboration)	.142	.062	1.179	2.294	.023

a. Dependent Variable: Transport Infrastructure

H5: International Collaboration Moderates the Relationship between Financial Support and Transport Infrastructure

From the table below it can be seen that the control variables significance value is not valid. For example, the significance value for experience is 0.820 which is not significant, that show the experience factor is controlled and it is not impacting the hypothesis results. Similarly, the firm size significant value is 0.800 that is not significant and showing that firm size is controlled and it is not impacting the overall hypothesis results. Further, the third control variables firm age and results states that firm age factor is controlled as well land not impacting the overall hypothesis results.

However, from the table below it can be seen that the significant value of interaction between government support and international collaboration is significant ($P < 0.01$) and the value of beta coefficient is positive (.210) that shows international collaboration positively moderates the relationship between government support and transport infrastructure.

Coefficients'

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.748	1.254		4.582	.000
Experience	-.013	.057	-.011	-.227	.820

Firm Size	.018	.071	.013	.254	.800
Firm Age	.098	.083	.058	1.178	.241
Government Support	1.244	.251	-1.195	-4.959	.000
International Collaboration	.067	.235	-.058	-.284	.777
Interaction (Government Support * International Collaboration)	.210	.046	1.717	4.578	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Transport Infrastructure

Summary

	Hypothesis	Supported/ not Supported
H1	Financial Support positively related to transport infrastructure	Supported
H2	Government Support positively related to transport infrastructure	Supported
H3	International Collaboration positively related to transport infrastructure	Supported
H4	International collaboration positively moderates the relationship between financial support and transport infrastructure.	Supported
H5	International collaboration positively moderates the relationship between government support and transport infrastructure.	Supported

Discussion

This study model focuses on moderating the effect of international collaboration in the relation among financial support, government support, and transport infrastructure. Data was collected, processed, and analyzed to test the study hypothesis. The summary presented in the table states that all of the hypotheses were supported.

International collaboration is used as a moderator for the first time between financial support and government support. To test this hypothesis data were collected from 153 respondents and the data was analyzed by using the SPSS analysis. Multiple regression analysis techniques are implemented and from the analysis results, it was concluded that international collaboration positively moderates the relationship between financial support, government support, and transport infrastructure. This hypothesis aligned with the previous research presented by Miguel et al., in 2018 in which it is stated that collaboration is the factor that contributes to the success of an organization. They further argue that when an organization collaborates, it increases the chances for the success of the business because collaboration increases or enhances the resources of the organization. further, this hypothesis is aligned with the research presented by Sandulli et al., 2017 in which it is stated that international collaboration relationships positively influence the infrastructure and for transport industry it is required to make international collaboration.

Further, at the start of this research, it was hypothesized that transportation industries with financial support capability seem to be more capable of contributing in improving the infrastructure of the transport. After applying the multiple regression analysis, it was found that financial support positively influences the transport infrastructure. This result is aligned with the research presented by West and Bogers in 2014. They have stated that organizations that are having strong financial support capabilities are more likely to contribute in the improvement of infrastructure (West and Bogers, 2014). This hypothesis was also aligned with the theoretical research presented by Wei in which they have stated that financial support along with the international collaboration are critical factor for improving the transport infrastructure (Wei et al., 2013). The second independent variable of the study is government support. From the statistical analysis, it is found that government support is positively associated with the transportation improvement.

This result is aligned with the research presented by Khazanchi, Lewis, and Boyer in 2007. In their research, they theoretically explained support from the governing bodies are positively related to the activities carried out to improve the infrastructure

H1. The financial support is positively related to transport infrastructure

After collecting data from the respondents and applying the regression analysis on the data set, this hypothesis was supported by the respondents. It is stated by Shen et al., in 2016 that financial support is positively related to the infrastructure improvements and this empirical evidence is aligned with the research presented by Shen and his co-fellows. Moreover, according to Atalay in 2013, financial support able organization to influence the performance of an organization, when an organization is having stronger financial support and is capable of dealing with the demands and needs of the customer's results in improved infrastructure. Further, for the developing countries to improve the businesses structure and economy, it is required to improve the transport infrastructure and for that, financial support is the critical factor to focus on (Yahya et al., 2013). According to Odumeru, 2013 the improvement in transport structure and the infrastructure highly depends on the of financial support, organizations which are having strong financial support are more likely to improve the transportation infrastructure.

From all these previous studies and literature, it is concluded that the organizations that financial support is a vital factor that contributes to the improvement in infrastructure. Organizations that are capable of innovating new products are more likely to be successful. All these theoretical studies were aligned with the first hypothesis of this study. To summarize, there is a strong correlation between the existing literature and our first hypothesis.

Not only for the transportation, but also for all of the activities that are carried out by organization, financial support is critical for success. Umar, Ji, Kirikkaleli and Xu stated that to improve the infrastructure of transportation financial support is critical (Umar et al., 2020). Further it is stated by Helm, and Thompson stated that the financial flexibility of the transportation is impacted the infrastructure improvement of the organization (Helm, and Thompson, 1991). Further, Deng in 2013, the financial support enable organizations to improve the infrastructure of the transportation model in the country as well as it enables organizations to influence the economic growth of the country. Practically we are having example China, that is a developed economy and the major element that contribute to the economic growth of the country. They took the initiative of belt and road through which they connected 145 countries.

The table below is a summary of research which are aligned with our research hypothesis

Table 6- 1 H1a Discussion

H1a. Financial support is positively related to the Transport infrastructure.		
Authors	Year	Theme
Shen et al.,	2016	Internal Innovation (Financial support) influence the performance of an organization
Nguyen	2019	Customer needs and demands fulfilment impact on transport infrastructure
Atalay	2013	Innovation activities influence the performance of an organization
Yahya et al.	2013	Implementation of external Knowledge in manufacturing of new products and services

H2a: The government support is positively related to transport infrastructure.

At the start of this research study, it was hypothesized that the government support is the critical factor for improving the transport infrastructure. Kanwal, Rasheed, Pitafi, and Ren, 2020 presented research in which it is stated that road developments the transport infrastructure highly depends on the government support as well as the support from the community (Kanwal, Rasheed, Pitafi, and Ren, 2020). When government support is provided to the transport

infrastructure, it is the greater probability that the transport system and infrastructure of that particular country will be improved. With the continuous increase in the population for the countries with poor transportation system it is necessary for the organizations to have support from the government bodies. As Bangladesh is a densely populated and low-lying nation. As of the 2021 report Bangladesh's population is around 167.89 million and this population is increasing by 10% annually. The total area of the country is 147 570 sq. km. this shows the population is dense and the major problem faced by the locals is related to transportation activities. It is obvious that in a dense population it will be difficult for the transportation industries to be challenged free. In Bangladesh, and for every country the role of transportation is very critical as this sector is growing exponentially for the last 20 years at the same time, transportation needs to keep changing its strategy to continuously grow and continuously improve its infrastructure. Around 62% of transportation services increase in the country, and with this increase, several challenges regarding the management of transportation systems are faced by the transportation sector. It is clear that the transportation sector of Bangladesh is not sufficient and efficient and they required strong improvements, therefore the role of the government is critical, organization should provide policies which are tax free for the transportation industry so they can contribute in the development of the nation. From this empirical research study, it is clear that the for the development of transportation infrastructure, the support from the government is critical for the success.

Another research conducted in African Sub Saharan country in which it is stated that the public private partnerships are required for the improvement of infrastructure of the transport. Further in this research study it is stated that transport infrastructure, rails, or roads impacted by the financial support and the governmental support (Chan, 2016). Further, in another research study it is stated that for the future economic growth and the development of the countries and to influence the trade it is required to improve the transport infrastructure, and for that government support and the financial support are the critical factor (Baccelli, 2020).

Increase in the local and the international trade which is one of the indicators for the transport infrastructure (Felker, Jomo, & Rasiah, 2013). Based on the previous researches it could be stated that the government support and the financial support both are critical factor in improving the transportation infrastructure.

From these two types of research it is concluded that the organizations that are effectively improving their processes result in improved performance, so, government support is a key factor for the success of an organization (Zailani, Govindan, Shaharudin, & Kuan, 2017). Government support results in achieving economies of scale that reduces the average cost and results in improved infrastructure of the transport (Christensen and Greene, 1976). This suggested hypothesis was aligned with all these researches and after collecting data, applying the regression analysis the hypothesis was supported. Therefore, the above mention studies are aligned with the hypothesis result.

The table below is showing the alignment between existing literature and this research's 2nd hypothesis.

Table 6 H2a Discussion

H2a. The government support capability of the firm is expected to influence transport infrastructure.		
Authors	Year	Theme
Kanwal, Rasheed, Pitafi, and Ren,	2020	Government support influence the transport infrastructure of the company
Singh et al.,	2016	Government support is critical factor in improving the transport infrastructure and the economic growth of the country.
Zailani, Govindan, Shaharudin, & Kuan,	2017	Government support activities influence the transportation and the development of a nation.

Christensen and Greene,	1976	Financial and government support are critical for the economic development and the growth of the nation.
Baccelli	2020	Economic growth and financial support are interdependent on each other
Felker, Jomo, & Rasiah,	2013	Economic development, international trade are interdependent on each other

H1b: International collaboration moderates the relationship between financial support and transport infrastructure

At the start of this research, it was hypothesized that international collaboration is the factor that strengthens the impact of financial support on the transport infrastructure. primary data was collected from the officials and the results state that there is a moderating role of international collaboration on transport infrastructure. International collaboration strives to improve long-term innovation and realize the true value of innovation in transportation is highly impacted by the international collaboration. When organizations collaborate with international institutions i.e. international financial institutions and developed countries it increases their chances that led to the successful improvements in the transportation infrastructure. Further, it is stated by Hongmei, Ying, and Jing, in 2020, that the transportation infrastructure is highly dependent on the external knowledge that can be achieved through international collaboration, or in other words it can be stated that organizations collaborate with international institutions to get assistance in term of financial aid as well as in term of guidance that increases the probability of success of transport infrastructure. This research by Hongmei, Ying, and Jing, in 2020 is aligned with our research hypothesis. Further, it is stated by Malone, Crowston in 1994, to develop and improve, innovate, to develop the transportation infrastructure collaboration is a critical factor, and it enhances the impact of financial support on the development of transport infrastructure (Malone and Crowston, 1994). As sustainability is the major factor that indicates the performance of an organization and according to Sezen and Çankaya (2013) the collaboration is the factor that helps in improving the innovation, and efficient transportation infrastructure (Sezen and Çankaya, 2013).

In 2011, another research presented by Yang, in 2011 it was stated that for the improvement of infrastructure of the transportation (Yang et al. 2011). For the economic development, economic growth and the sustainable development of the organizations, only financial support is not enough, because most of the underdeveloped countries it is required for the firms to collaborate with international partners that can assist in assuring the success of projects therefore the implementation the international involvement is critical to improve the processes of transport infrastructure. In this research this it was hypothesized that the international collaboration moderates the relationship between financial support and the transportation infrastructure.

It is stated in previous studies that the potential of a transportation industry to get involved in international collaboration improves its competitiveness and performance as well as the infrastructure (Prage et al., 2015). Inter-organization collaboration helps in improving the infrastructure of transportation system as well as of an organization (De Araújo Burcharth et al., 2014). With the increase in populations, the needs and demands of the customers are increased and it became difficult for the countries to sustain by using the poor transportation system and for that the under-developed countries needs to collaborate with developed nations. for instance, Bangladesh which is an under-developed country therefore it should collaborate with the developed nations i.e. China in which the transportation sector has been improved since last two decades therefore the involvement of China in the Bangladeshi transportation improve its infrastructure. In addition, to be successful in the competitive market organizations needs to be more focused on financial support, and according to resources based view theory, organizations that collaborate with others are having the chance to improve their resources and enhance the innovation rate (Prange et al., 2015). Based on these

researches it can be clear that the international collaboration is a critical factor that enhances the impact of financial support on the improved infrastructure of the country.

Only financial support is not the key to success, but the rate at which an organization is innovating is also an important factor that contributes to the success of an organization and collaboration is the factor that speeds up the innovation within an organization (Langerak et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2010). The success of an infrastructure depends on three-factor which are the cost of the product, the functionality of the product, and the time to deliver the product to the customers, and collaboration is the factor that contributes to enhancing all these factors together (McGinnis et al., 1999; Swink, 1999).

It is argued by another author Supplier expertise and technical knowledge can improve effectiveness and efficiency (Weggeman et al., 2001). International collaboration accelerates the rate of innovation, allowing businesses to put products to market ahead of their competition. As a result, rather than becoming followers, businesses become proactive and market leaders. (Óscar et al., 2019). International collaboration improves the brainstorming process and produces a huge number of innovative ideas and plans. An organization can have the appropriate path in terms of innovation via collaborating (Chen et al., 2010).

From all of the above-mentioned researches, it is clear that when transportation sector of Bangladesh collaborate with other countries with high quality infrastructure can help organizations to improve their infrastructure. In the table below the summary of the previous literature is mentioned and this table gives an overview of how previous kinds of literature are aligned with our research hypothesis.

Table 7 H1b Discussion

H1b. International collaboration moderates the relationship between financial support and transport infrastructure.		
Authors	Year	Theme
Hongmei, Ying, and Jing	2020	Collaboration enhances the transportation sector.
Malone and Crowston in	1994	Collaboration improves transport infrastructure by impacting the sustainable innovation
Zailani, Govindan, Shaharudin, & Kuan,	2017	Government support activities influence the performance of an organization
Christensen and Greene,	1976	Government support help in achieving economies of scale and improved performance
Sezen and Çankaya	2013	Collaboration results in improving the innovation performance
Yang et al.	2011	Collaboration practices influence financial support rate and transport infrastructure
Prage et al.,	2015	Collaboration impact the competitiveness of an organization
Prange et al.,	2015	Improved infrastructure are the result of collaboration
Chen et al.,	2010	Collaboration speeds up the transportation infrastructure
Langerak et al.,	2005	Collaboration speeds up the infrastructure improvement of transportation

McGinnis et al.,	1999	International collaboration, results in the improved infrastructure and drive improvement in low cost
Swink, 1999	1999	Improved functionality of the new product depends on collaboration
Weggeman et al.	2001	Collaboration with developed countries help organizations to improve the transportation infrastructure
Óscar et al.,	2019	Collaboration enhances the impact of financial support on the transport infrastructure
Chen et al.,	2010	Collaboration help transportation sector to took right decisions.

H2b: International collaboration moderates the relationship between government support and transport infrastructure

International collaboration is a critical factor that influence the impact of government support on the transportation infrastructure. Transportation organization needs to collaborate with international institutions to get the financial support and this is not possible without government support and government involvement is required to include the international bodies that can help in improving the transportation infrastructure. The international collaboration among nations it is required to involve the government because there are several policies and paper work that needs to be done, secondly when there is international collaboration it financially support the process and the impact of government support on transportation infrastructure can be improved. As this research study is conducted on Bangladesh which is a densely populated country and the local population is facing problems related to the transportations sector therefore they need to improve their transportation infrastructure not only for their economic development but also to satisfy their customers

Research Limitations

In this research author have collected data from 153 respondents which are working in different transportation industries and working on development and improvement of infrastructure, but in future the data can be collected from at least 500 respondents and then that data should be analyzed because increase data set with help in generalizing the effect. Further, this research is based on the respondents working in transportation industries, but in future the data can be collected from local publics to address what are the major problems are being faced by them and then transportation sector can take actions to solve those specific problems. Further this research contains the statistical analysis and statistical methods, in future research extensively literature focused researches can be carried out and the mathematical modeling can be adopted to not only to address the problem but also to proposed the solution regarding transport infrastructure. Further U-Shaped and Inverted U-shaped statistical analysis techniques can be adopted to run the regression analysis.

Research Implications

Bangladesh is a developing economy, and the country's economic progress is dependent on its transportation infrastructure. Bangladesh's main challenge at the moment is that it has a little land area and a large population. Bangladesh's dense population necessitated a huge number of automobiles, and the country's infrastructure must be improved to accommodate this. This component will also be investigated in this study, making it even more important. Bangladesh need considerable financial and development assistance from both the corporate and public sectors to upgrade its infrastructure. Bangladesh BRT will need to partner with other nations for financial assistance in order to solve the investment hurdles. The CPEC model, for example, can be emulated; CPEC is a joint venture between Pakistan

and China. This corridor will aid Pakistan's (growing economy) transportation infrastructure, resulting in the country's economic progress. This outcome will investigate the influence of international collaboration and how it improves the impact of transportation expenditures. This is the research's initial significance. This is the first sign of this research. Further how government support towards the private road construction will help this sector will be elaborated and it will make this research more significant. Second, a country's economic progress is determined by the firms that operate there. Different transportation operations for the movement of products and services are included in enterprises, and a sustainable and high-quality transportation system is a significant aspect in an organization's success. During the Covid-19 scenario, for example, the majority of enterprises failed due to unsustainable transportation infrastructure. Organizations were unable to get raw materials from their suppliers and deliver their products to their clients. Because to a lack of raw materials and a nationwide lockdown, most international car businesses in Bangladesh, such as Suzuki Motors, were unable to sell or build a single product.

Furthermore, with the advent of e-commerce, buyers want things to arrive at their doorsteps on time, from both local and foreign businesses. For example, Alibaba is a platform that delivers items in Asian nations, and quality infrastructure is required for on-time product delivery. As a result of e-commerce, the demand for high-quality transportation infrastructure has risen, and this research focuses on enhancing the transportation system's infrastructure, making this research study more relevant.

The transportation infrastructure of a nation has an influence on all of the companies functioning in that country; for example, most enterprises have suppliers in various areas, cities, and even countries. Because of poor transportation infrastructure and lower road capacity compared to actual demands, the major problem faced by organizations is on-time delivery of products or raw materials to manufacturers. As a result, transportation plays a critical role in improving the performance of other businesses. This study is especially important because of the influence of transportation on other industries.

Conclusion

This research is empirical in nature, and for this research study author have collected data from individuals that are working in transportation industries and then author have implemented regression analysis to identify the impact of financial support and government support impact on the transportation infrastructure. Further, the secondary objective of this research study is to identify the moderating role of international collaboration on the relationship between financial support and government support, on the transportation infrastructure of the company. Results states the government support and financial support are critical driving in the transportation infrastructure. Further the secondary objective of the research is to identify the moderating role of international collaboration and statistical results states that international collaboration strengthens the impact of financial support on transportation infrastructure. Further this research study enriches the existing literature by providing the empirical evidence that international collaboration strengthens the impact of government support in the transportation infrastructure. Further this research is conducted in Bangladesh, and to the best of author knowledge before no empirical evidence is conducted in Bangladesh therefore the output of this research will enrich the existing literature.

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